

PLASTOME ANALYSIS OF THE PARASITIC INDIAN OLIVE
(*NESTRONIA UMBELLULA*)

By

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Abstract

Parasitic plants exploit their hosts for water and nutrients, often resulting in a decreased reliance on photosynthetic processes. Increased levels of parasitism are associated with relaxed evolutionary pressure to photosynthesize, often resulting in dramatic changes to the chloroplast genome (i.e. plastome). Santalales is an order of angiosperms containing over 2000 species in 18 families, with species representing all ranges of parasitism, from nonparasitic to hemiparasitic and holoparasitic. Members of this order include sandalwoods and mistletoes, both economically and culturally important species. Using Geneious R9, we sequenced and annotated the plastome of *Nestronia umbellula* and compared it with relatives to examine the evolution of gene losses associated with parasitism in the Santalales. We found that this species' genome contains an average GC content and lower number of genes than the compared species. Comparing the suite of genomes revealed the holoparasite to have a lower GC content than the chosen six Santalales. Information will be used in future studies to clarify phylogenetic relationships within the order.

Keywords:

Parasitic plants, Santalales, Plastome Evolution, *Nestronia umbellula*

Introduction

Photosynthesis occurs within the chloroplast of a plant cell. Here, chlorophyll A, among other accessory pigments, utilize sunlight, water, and carbon dioxide to store ATP energy for the plant. In contrast, parasitic plants exploit their host plants for water and nutrients using a connective organ called the 'haustoria'. Parasitism occurs as a direct result of water unavailability; it is not known to be present in aquatic environments (Rubiales and Heide-Jorgensen 2011). This lifestyle has evolved over 11 times in angiosperms (Barkman et. al 2007) and can be considered one of the most successful (Westwood et. al 2010) due to the low investment of energy.

Several levels of parasitism exist. Non-parasitic species rely on photosynthesis for energy, while hemiparasitic species derive at least some nutrients or water from their hosts. Holoparasitic plants rely solely on their hosts. These are not able to photosynthesize due to a lack of chlorophyll.

Both facultative and obligate species can survive without exploiting a host, but only facultative species can complete their life cycle without parasitizing another plant. Generalists can survive on a variety of different hosts, while specialists can only survive on one host species or species closely related to their preferred host. Stem parasites can be found attached to the trunk or the branches of a host, while root parasites affect the underground portions.

These subcategories do not necessarily fully encompass the wide range of parasitism some species may exhibit. Parasite characteristics may be a combination of the above or an intermediate phenotype.

In order for a parasitic lifestyle to be successful, its haustorium must make contact with the host stele (Yoder 1999, Shen et. al 2006). This connection allows for the flow of solutes between the two individuals by physically connecting each individuals' vascular system. The adventitious root only develops when the individual seed or seedling comes into contact with unstabilized signaling molecules from an appropriate host (Yoder 1999); these molecules are therefore called 'Haustorium Inducing Factors' (HIFs) (Shen et. al 2006). High numbers of unstabilized molecules are indicative of close proximity to the host, since distance between the individuals allows for the molecules to become stable as time elapses (Yoder 1999).

The parasite's lack of nutrients and high transpiration rate work in its favor— the laws of diffusion move precious nutrients into the barren parasite without any other effort. Once this advantage is exhausted, the haustorium then prevents ions from flowing backwards from the parasite to the host (Rubiales and Heide-Jorgensen 2011).

Evolutionary Forces and Plastome Reduction

According to the molecular clock hypothesis, species' genomes experience comparable rates of nucleotide substitution (Nickrent and Duff 1996). In the case of autotrophic plants, researchers are able to clarify species' relationships and create phylogenetic trees based on data from the chloroplast genome. However, a parasitic lifestyle relaxes evolutionary constraints on the parasite's photosynthetic processes, allowing these genes to degrade more quickly (Vidal-Russel 2008 and Westwood et. al 2010).

Plastome reduction occurs when genes disappear altogether, shortening the genome from one generation to the next (Nickrent et. al 1998). Parasitic plants generally lose photosynthetic genes. These genes are not needed, and are slowly degraded as the generations pass. Identifying degradation trajectories is necessary for identifying genetic clades.

Parasite Morphology

Basing a phylogenetic tree on parasitic plant morphology does not clarify relationships. Photosynthetic gene degradation leads to the loss of photosynthetic organs. In advanced parasites, leaves have become reduced to scales, and these types of species likely also have experienced a loss of chlorophyllous perianth parts and ovular integuments, among other losses (Nickrent et. al 1998). In short, there are too few parts on which to infer phylogenetic relationships. Adequate morphology is not present, and thus cannot be studied in depth for these purposes.

The Molecular Clock

Plant cells contain three distinct genomes from (1) the chloroplast, (2) the mitochondria, and (3) the nucleus. Traditionally, researchers use the concept of the molecular clock to place species into a phylogenetic tree, however, this method cannot reliably be used with plants (Nickrent and Duff 1996). Parasitic plants are especially unique because of the high nucleotide substitution rate in their nuclear genomes. Photosynthetic genes are highly susceptible to gene degradation because the plant is not reliant on its own energy production. Because of this accelerated loss of genes, the molecular clock hypothesis is not appropriate for dating species divergences for an accurate phylogeny.

Horizontal Gene Transfer

Horizontal gene transfer (HGT) is characterized by the movement and integration of DNA across species boundaries (Yang et. al 2019). In plants, these events are hypothesized to arise from the reverse transcription of exchanged RNA molecules through the haustorial phloem connection (Yang et. al 2019). Observation of a host genome reveals the presence of both introns and exons in the gene, while matching HGT genes found in the parasite lack these introns (Yang et. al 2019).

Higher numbers of HGT events are found in obligate parasites as compared to facultative parasites (Yang et. al 2016). Because obligate parasites must come into physical contact with their hosts to germinate, the intimate haustorial connection facilitates gene transfer in these developing seedlings. Facultative parasites are more mature when this connection is established, thus, these plants do not easily accept HGTs from the host. As a result, HGT events tend to be more complex (Yang et. al 2016). Thus, as the degree of parasitism increases along the phylogenetic tree, it is expected that more HGT events will have occurred.

Pseudogenization and Gene Loss

Deleterious base pair substitutions and mutations commonly occur in all replicating organisms. Individuals which experience negative genetic divergences will fail. Because these individuals likely do not reproduce, these mutations quickly disappear from the population. Only genes which are beneficial to a species' survival are maintained.

Photosynthetic genes are often not necessary for parasitic plants to survive. As the generations pass, photosynthetic genes are neutralized by an accumulation of mutations. Decayed genes, or pseudogenes, are visible in the genetic material of the organism. Their sequence may be close to the original, but these genes are non-functional. Gene loss occurs when the pseudogene is decayed beyond recognition, or when the gene is left completely out (not copied from the parent cell to the daughters), resulting in a shorter genetic sequence.

Santalales

The Santalales are angiosperms composed of 2000 distinct species within 18 different families. All ranges of parasitism are represented within these species (non-, hemi-, and holoparasites). Santalales are considered to be a major parasitic lineage; this family includes the parasitic mistletoes (and dwarf mistletoes), which are culturally associated with Christmas in the Western hemisphere (Nickrent 2001, and Mathiasen et. al 2008). Sandalwoods are also a part of this order, and are economically important for their use in making essential oils (Visser 1918 and Tennakoon and Cameron 2016) for commercial products.

Nestronia umbellula

Nestronia umbellula, or the Indian olive, is a perennial root hemiparasite in the Santalaceae family. It is native to the south-eastern United States. As of June 2020, the United States Department of Agriculture has listed the plant as threatened in Georgia, and endangered in Kentucky, Tennessee and Virginia (USDA 2020).

Researching and publishing the *Nestronia* genome will supplement the growing number of annotated parasitic plant genomes. There are 36 published Santalales chloroplast genomes available on NCBI's GenBank, a peer reviewed online database where DNA sequences are publicly available (Chen et. al 2020). The genetic sequences of parasitic plants are not well documented, and their evolutionary trajectory is not well understood. Making the *Nestronia* genome accessible to researchers will allow for more accurate phylogenetic hypotheses and higher quality research to occur.

Figure 1. A specimen *Nestronia umbellula*. Photo by Mark Pistang

Methods

Sample Collection and Sequencing

Wild *Nestronia umbellula* tissue (Der144) was collected in Duke Forest on the grounds of Duke University (36.0014° N, 78.9382° W) in Durham, North Carolina. Fresh tissue was silica dried before DNA extraction.

DNA extraction was performed using the DNeasy Plant Mini kit by Qiagen.

DNA concentration was validated using the Invitrogen Qubit dsDNA high sensitivity assay and normalized to approximately 15-20 ng/μL. Illumina TruSeq-compatible genomic DNA libraries were prepared for Illumina HiSeq by Global Biologics (Columbia, MO). Libraries were created using the Touchless Total Prep System, a library preparation system which eliminates problems associated with manual and standard liquid handling processes. Libraries were created using SPRI size selection targeting ~450bp insert, then equimolar volumes of 48 libraries were pooled for size selection using the PippinHT system to provide ~470bp insert. Sequencing was performed on the Illumina HiSeq 2500 in Rapid Mode to obtain paired 250bp reads.

Genome Assembly and Annotation

De novo assembly of the chloroplast genome was performed using NOVOplasty (Dierckxsens et. al 2017).

Our *Nestronia umbellula* genome was then processed against several related genomes in a Geneious R9 implemented Mauve alignment. Gene coordinates in *Nestronia umbellula* were identified by sequence similarity to genes in the species *Olex imbricata* and *Santalum album*. All tRNA anticodons, start, and end positions were identified with tRNAscan-SE (Lowe 1997, Lowe 2016). If the sequence did not code for a product, the annotation was marked as a “-like” gene, or pseudogene. The final annotation table was downloaded from Geneious into an excel sheet. The table was processed in Microsoft Excel for total gene number, number of genes per category, and number of pseudogenes.

Analyzing the Genome

GC content and sequence length were calculated using Geneious V9. These categories were found using default settings. Tandem repeats greater than 20 bp in length were identified by the Geneious plugin “Repeat Finder ” using 5% maximum mismatches. Repeats 5 bp longer than the contained repeat were excluded. In order to gain a wider understanding of how *Nestronia* compares to its immediate relatives, the genome was compared against several other species across the Santalales family, representing the full range of parasitism. The holoparasite *Rhopalocnemis phalloides* was not included when calculating averages; these data points were considered outliers.

Results

Table 1. Genes present in the *Nestronia umbellula* genome, identified using Geneious V9. Of the 103 genes, there are 26 photosynthesis genes, 62 genes related to the translation apparatus and 14 ATP genes. Four pseudogenes are present.

Name	Product	Length (bp)	% GC
Photosynthesis Genes			
psaA CDS	photosystem I P700 apoprotein A1	2,253	42.70
psaB CDS	photosystem I P700 apoprotein A2	2,205	40.70
psaC CDS	photosystem I subunit VII	246	42.70
psaJ CDS	photosystem I subunit IX	135	37.80
psal CDS	photosystem I subunit VIII	117	30.80
psbA CDS	photosystem II protein D1	1,062	41.60
psbB CDS	photosystem II 47 kDa protein	1,527	44.00
psbC CDS	photosystem II CP43 chlorophyll apoprotein	1,422	44.50
psbD CDS	photosystem II protein D2	1,062	43.70
psbE CDS	photosystem II cytochrome b559 alpha subunit	252	40.50
psbF CDS	photosystem II cytochrome b559 beta subunit	120	40.80
psbH CDS	photosystem II phosphoprotein	240	34.60
psbJ CDS	photosystem II protein J	123	39.00
psbK CDS	photosystem II protein K	198	37.90
psbL CDS	photosystem II protein L	117	30.80
psbI CDS	photosystem II protein I	111	39.60
psbM CDS	photosystem II protein M	105	33.30
psbN CDS	photosystem II protein N	132	43.90
psbT CDS	photosystem II protein T	108	31.50
psbZ CDS	photosystem II protein Z	189	34.40
ycf1 CDS	putative chloroplast RF1	5,646	29.40
ycf3 CDS	putative chloroplast RF34	507	39.40
ycf4 CDS	photosystem I assembly protein ycf4	555	38.40
cemA CDS	chloroplast envelope membrane protein	689	31.30

rbcL CDS	ribulose 1,5-bisphosphate carboxylase/oxygenase large subunit	1,428	43.90
accD CDS	acetyl-CoA carboxylase carboxyltransferase beta subunit	1,464	35.70

ATP Genes

atpA CDS	ATP synthase CF1 alpha subunit	1,542	40.80
atpB CDS	ATP synthase CF1 beta subunit	1,497	42.60
atpE CDS	ATP synthase CF1 epsilon subunit	402	40.80
atpF CDS	ATP synthase CF0 subunit I	555	36.60
atpH CDS	ATP synthase CF0 subunit III	246	44.70
atpI CDS	ATP synthase CF0 subunit IV	744	38.00
petA CDS	cytochrome f	969	38.70
petB CDS	cytochrome b6	648	39.70
petD CDS	cytochrome b6/f complex subunit IV	483	36.90
petG CDS	cytochrome b6/f complex subunit V	114	34.20
petL CDS	cytochrome b6/f complex subunit VI	96	28.10
petN CDS	cytochrome b6/f complex subunit VIII	90	42.20
ccsA CDS	c-type cytochrome synthesis protein	972	32.10
ccsA CDS	cytochrome c heme attachment protein	933	35.20

Translation Apparatus

rpoA CDS	RNA polymerase alpha subunit	1,008	34.50
rpoB CDS	RNA polymerase beta subunit	3,219	39.40
rpoC1 CDS	RNA polymerase beta	2,046	38.20
rpoC2 CDS	RNA polymerase beta" subunit	4,101	38.30
rpl2 CDS	ribosomal protein L2	828	44.10
rpl14 CDS	ribosomal protein L14	369	39.80
rpl16 CDS	ribosomal protein L16	408	42.90
rpl20 CDS	ribosomal protein L20	354	36.70
rpl22 CDS	ribosomal protein L22	480	36.00
rpl23 CDS	ribosomal protein L23	282	37.90
rpl32 CDS	ribosomal protein L32	153	37.30

rpl33 CDS	ribosomal protein L33	204	37.30
rpl36 CDS	ribosomal protein L36	114	36.00
rps2 CDS	ribosomal protein S2	711	38.40
rps3 CDS	ribosomal protein S3	657	35.00
rps4 CDS	ribosomal protein S4	606	39.40
rps7 CDS	ribosomal protein S7	468	40.20
rps8 CDS	ribosomal protein S8	408	35.50
rps11 CDS	ribosomal protein S11	417	44.60
rps12 CDS	ribosomal protein S12	794	39.70
rps12 CDS	ribosomal protein S12	372	43.40
rps14 CDS	ribosomal protein S14	303	41.30
rps15 CDS	ribosomal protein S15	276	30.40
rps16 CDS	ribosomal protein S16	252	36.50
rps18 CDS	ribosomal protein S18	357	35.30
rps19 CDS	ribosomal protein S19	279	35.50
rrn4.5 rRNA	4.5S ribosomal RNA	103	52.40
rrn5 rRNA	5S ribosomal RNA	121	52.90
rrn16 rRNA	16S ribosomal RNA	1,491	56.60
rrn23 rRNA	23S ribosomal RNA	2,808	55.20
trn-Ala tRNA	tRNA-Alanine	73	56.20
trnC-GCA tRNA	tRNA-Cysteine	71	60.60
trnD-GUC tRNA	tRNA-Aspartic Acid	71	62.00
trnE-UUC gene	tRNA-Glutamic Acid	73	58.90
trnF-GAA tRNA	tRNA-Phenylalanine	73	52.10
trnfM-CAU tRNA	tRNA-Methionine	74	56.80
trnG-UCC tRNA	tRNA-Glycine	71	52.10
trnG-UCC tRNA	tRNA-Glycine	70	48.60
trnH-GUG tRNA	tRNA-Histidine	74	58.10
trnI-CAU tRNA	tRNA-Isoleucine	74	45.90

trnI-GAU tRNA	tRNA-Isoleucine	77	59.70
trnL-CAA tRNA	tRNA-Leucine	80	57.50
trnL-UAA tRNA	tRNA-Leucine	87	47.10
trnL-UAG gene	tRNA-Leucine	80	57.50
trnM-CAU tRNA	tRNA-Methionine	73	43.80
trnP-UGG tRNA	tRNA-Proline	75	46.70
trnQ-UUG tRNA	tRNA-Glutamine	72	59.70
trnR-ACG tRNA	tRNA-Arginine	74	63.50
trnR-UCU tRNA	tRNA-Arginine	72	41.70
trnS-GCU tRNA	tRNA-Serine	88	53.40
trnS-GGA tRNA	tRNA-Serine	87	50.60
trnS-UGA tRNA	tRNA-Serine	93	50.50
trnT-GGU tRNA	tRNA-Threonine	72	50.00
trnT-UGU tRNA	tRNA-Threonine	73	50.70
trnV-GAC tRNA	tRNA-Valine	72	45.80
trnV-UAC tRNA	tRNA-Valine	76	51.30
trnW-CCA tRNA	tRNA-Tryptophan	74	51.40
trnY-GUA tRNA	tRNA-Tyrosine	84	56.00
ttrnN-GUU tRNA	tRNA-Asparagine	72	55.60
matK CDS	maturase K	1,512	33.70
clpP CDS	clp protease proteolytic subunit	591	41.10
infA CDS	translation initiation factor 1	231	34.60
Others			
orf42 CDS	ribosomal protein S5	75	60.00
orf42 CDS	ribosomal protein S5	129	52.70
ycf15 CDS	chloroplast RF15	300	38.00
ycf2 CDS	chloroplast RF21	6,867	37.70
		Total:	60,336 bp

Table 2. Summary of seven Santalales representatives, including *Nestronia umbellula*. Data from the holoparasite *Rhopalocnemis phalloides* was not included in the averages. Species without accession numbers are not published under GenBank.

	<i>Nestronia umbellula</i>	<i>Rhopalocnemis phalloides</i>	<i>Olax imbricata</i>	<i>Osyris alba</i>	<i>Santalum album</i>	<i>Viscum album</i>	<i>Vitis Rotundifolia</i>	
GenBank Accession	-	MK036331	-	KT070882	MN414167	KT003925	NC_023790	average
Family	Santalaceae	Balanophoraceae	Olacaceae	Santalaceae	Santalaceae	Viscaceae	Vitaceae	
Parasitism	Root Hemi	Holoparasite	Root Hemi	Root Hemi	Root Hemi	Stem Hemi	Non	
Length (bp)	148,149	18,622	155,798	147,253	144,034	128,921	168,891	148,841
# genes	103	16	124	117	119	115	129	118
# pseudo	4	1	13	0	13	0	2	5
# repeats	46	400	318	53	67	231	111	138
% genic	45.36	78.93	60.71	53.60	60.38	59.09	52.48	55.27
% GC content	37.60	11.20	35.80	37.70	36.40	36.40	37.40	36.88

Figure 2. *Nostonia umbellula* circular genome. Plastome map was generated by OG Draw. Color legend identifies gene function categories. Of the outer map, genes outside the circle are transcribed clockwise, while genes inside the circle are transcribed counterclockwise. Inverted repeats (IRA and IRB), long single copy (LSC) and short single copy (SSC) are outlined by the inner map. GC content is also described by the inner map.

The genome has 103 protein coding genes total, which is less than the calculated average of 118. The genome is more than 20,000 bp shorter than its autotroph relative, *Vitis rotundifolia*, at 148,149 bp to *Vitis*' 168,891 bp. Of *Nestronia umbellula*'s functioning genes, photosynthetic genes make up 26. Genes related to translation are most frequent at 62, and 14 genes code for manufacturing ATP. Four pseudogenes were found. One pseudogene is present in the IRs; its function would be to code for a ribosomal protein. The other two degraded genes would code each code for different photosynthetic pigments.

The genome's large single copy (LSC) region is 83,124 bp in length. The short single copy (SSC) region is 13,320 bp. Both inverted repeat (IR) regions are 25,853 bps. The *Nestronia* genome was thus found to be 148,149 bp in total length, with a 37.6% GC content. The sequence was also found to contain 46 repeats.

Across the representative Santalales, average genome length was 141,413 bp, with 69,699 genes, or an average 57.44% genic rate. These species had an average of 9 pseudogenes; while this number is slightly less than the mean of the species considered (5), two of the five hemiparasites contain 13 pseudogenes. Mean GC content was calculated to be 36.40%. Mean tandem repeats were calculated at 131. Overall, these species had an average repeat percentage of 0.09.

Discussion

As a hemiparasite, *Nestronia umbellula* has a smaller proportion of its genome made up of genes (45.63 %) than the calculated Santalales average (58.65 %), likely due the degradation of genes related to energy synthesis. The loss of length can similarly be attributed to plastome reduction, at which the parasitic genome experiences the loss of an entire gene. Photosynthetic genes are likely to have been cut from the *Nestronia* genome. Two of the four pseudogenes each code for different photosynthetic pigments which allow the species to collect energy from wavelengths of light. Their presence as visibly decayed genes supports the aforementioned hypothesis. The last two pseudogenes (these have the same genetic sequence, as they are present in the IR) aid in protein synthesis. It is unclear whether these pseudogenes would be involved in creating photosynthetic pigments, or if their use as ribosomal subunits extends generally to all proteins. A more complex analysis of these pseudogenes and the parallel genes of *Nestronia*'s relatives would be necessary to confirm their function.

The genome of *Nestronia umbellula* contains 37.60% GC content with 103 genes. These numbers are similar for the six Santalales considered, including the autotrophic *Vitis rotundifolia* (mean %GC: 36.88, number of genes: 118). In contrast, the holoparasitic relative, *Rhopalocnemis phalloides*, was found to have an outlying 11.20% GC content, and a mere 16 functioning genes. The low %GC content of this holoparasite may be explained by the absence of its photosynthetic sequences, therefore, the close-to-average %GC content of *Nestronia* may be attributed to the maintenance of its photosynthetic genes. A wider analysis of GC content across the Santalales, including an analysis of all holoparasites, would be necessary to support this hypothesis.

The low number of tandem repeats (46) suggests that the *Nestronia* genome is less susceptible than its relatives (mean: 138) to mutations due to misaligned combination and subsequent replication (Meyers 2007). The two additional root hemiparasites have similar numbers (*Osyris alba*: 53, *Santalum album*: 67), while those outside the Santalaceae family contain numbers in the triple digits. As expected, the holoparasitic species contains the greatest number of tandem repeats (400). Within this data set, low numbers of tandem repeats are unique to the Santalaceae family, and likely indicate a change or difference in the family's evolutionary history. It would be interesting to explore this hypothesis by considering all species within the Santalaceae against all other species in the Santalales order.

The annotation of *Nestronia umbellula* is vital in understanding the evolutionary trajectory of parasitic plants, especially those within the Santalales. Comparing species within the order can define patterns in genetics. As aforementioned, 36 species of Santalales have been sequenced and published of the 2000+ known species. A more complete set of annotations will allow researchers more information on which to extrapolate relationships, as well as understand and predict evolutionary trajectories. Because this order is a major parasitic lineage, it is likely that hypotheses generated from this information will easily translate towards other orders containing parasites. Similarities and differences among these orders are important to identify; parasitic lineages and research into their unique genetic trajectories is underrepresented.

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